

Freedom of Information and Democracy: an Interdependent Relationship and the Role Internet can Play.

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Abstract

This paper addresses issues of interdependence between democracy and information. On the basis that information means knowledge and knowledge possession implies power, we examine the importance of free and immediate information access in a democracy; a state that aids citizens evaluate, take part and exercise actively and freely political rights and obligations. Methods employed by dictatorships to control information and the importance they attach to its exploitation in propaganda, set as a paradigm to reach to the conclusion that free access to information is an enemy of totalitarian regimes and strategic ally of well-governed and effective democracies.

How can we experience boundless and independent media (newspapers - radios - TV channels) when information is in the hands of entrepreneurs and factions associated directly or indirectly with various political forces? When many TV channels and newspapers act often as mouthpieces of various political parties with which they interact? Is this an important complication for democracy and a moral-ethic issue of free information dissemination? How does it differ from propaganda in totalitarian regimes?

Perhaps the only information medium that remains direct and independent, is Internet, where citizens have direct, free information through numerous blogs and webpages. In ostensibly democratic regimes experiencing frustrating political situations, Internet can be the biggest ally of democracy, giving it its true essence, which is the right to freedom of information and expression.

Keywords

Information, Democracy, Ethics, Internet, Propaganda

Introduction

The power and importance of access to information needs no proof. Throughout centuries, the control of timely and reliable information was an important factor of political power (Bohman, 1996). He, who could control and holds the real information, has the privilege to be one step forward of his political opponents and to direct the people who he rules. Over the centuries and reaching today -the era of Internet- instant information access and the value and importance of information in general, are major issues creating new opportunities and challenges. In countries with democratic culture and past, intense Internet use create conditions for debates on the quality of the current state of democracy and prospect towards greater citizen immediacy and involvement to politics. Conversely, in states with consciousness and culture of authoritarian regimes, major issue is control of information and in particular Internet use, towards maintaining focus away from a delusion of democratization.

All these reveal direct ties between information and democracy. Timely and accurate information can provide the opportunity to the citizen seek and ask for the deserved power in a democratic environment or the ability and consciousness to gain civil rights in an authoritarian regime.

In this paper, we examine the relationship and interaction among information and democracy along with Internet's potential towards freedom of information and thus, towards dynamic, participatory democracy. Furthermore, we observe the relationship among *information* and *propaganda* and among *media* and politics. Additionally, we explore extremist demeanor emerging from *group polarization* as well as Internet and social media *personalization* placing obstacles to democracy, since democratic sentiment is based on socialization, common consciousness, social solidarity and responsibility. As a final point, we discuss the importance and dangers of *filtering* huge volumes of Internet information.

1.1. Information and Democracy

Amongst principal democratic values are freedom of expression and freedom and independence of the media. According to Dahl (1971) eight basic principles of democracy are 1) freedom to form and join organizations 2) freedom of expression 3) active right to vote 4) passive right to vote (eligibility for public office) 5) right of political leaders to compete for support and for votes 6) access to information from multiple sources (alternative sources of information) 7) free and fair elections 8) institutions for making government policies depend on votes and other expressions of preferences. Amongst these principles are those related to freedom of information and media pluralism forming the backbone of democracy. As Mohrenberg (2011) notes:

“In democracies, open media are the lifeblood of civil society and political opposition.”

By definition, democracy is a civil polity by people and for people (Brennan et. al., 1993) and in order to properly function, needs citizens with developed critical thinking combined with awareness of social responsibility. Since democracy is a political system made by citizens and for citizens themselves, often is not protected by connoisseurs and professional politicians. Instead, citizens themselves must be activated to move in a direction, where the political system can operate efficiently (Lombardini, 2013) and secure democratic values. Two most important factors composing such a democratic consciousness of social and political responsibility are education and information. In this paper we are looking at information, although these two (education and information) are strongly connected, since the educational processes form consciences and impressions to citizens. Often, this ability and process is contrary to the democratic role media possess, since certain political powers control media.

Information is crucial to a well-governed democracy. Through information the citizen is shaping consciousness and perspective on current affairs, of political or social interest. As Dennis McQuail (1979) notes:

“On the one hand, there is a provision of a consistent picture of the social world which may lead the audience to adopt this version of reality, a reality of ‘facts’ and of norms, values and expectations. On the other hand, there is a continuing and selective interaction between self and the media which plays a part in shaping the individual’s own behavior and self-concept”

This illustrates how sensitive information and media is, since general political and social opinion-consciousness when directed, compose an important political-democratic tool (McQuail, 1979). In the current form of Western state representative democracy, information and media are serving people to control actions of politicians (Bimber, 2003). This assumes media independence -a very important state democracy index- from political and/or private interests. A state democracy controlling information ceases to serve its purposes and flirts with authoritarian practices. When citizens are misinformed on political reality, they lose political power and hence the possibility to question state polity.

Information is crucial in a democracy as it has the power to “guide” public opinion and form trends. Real, unbiased information provision is a constructive tool for citizens, since it offers the possibility of control on political acts and legislation and intermediary between citizens and politicians, making the common intention known to politicians and the acts of politicians, known to citizens (Bimber, 2003). None of this can happen without the exchange of information and the intermediary role that the media should have. In an analogy, what was the “Agora” for ancient Athens, for today's

democracies are numerous sites providing information. The sites of conciliation and thought, where opinions can be formed and decisions can be taken, serving the common intention of the municipality. In a democracy, information is a right and a measure of the quality of the political life. Wiener (1964) aptly notes:

“To live effectively is to live with adequate information. Thus, communication and control belong to the essence of man’s inner life, even as they belong to his life in society.”

In a civil polity, such as democracy, citizens have the right and must be objectively informed on the happenings of the political life of their country. When the individual loses touch with power, then by definition, no longer is interested in politics. Lack of sufficient information, constitutes isolation and sense of lost power of control that democracy, by definition, should provide. This results to gradual citizen removal from politics and in the end, the final indifference (Peabody, 1905). Very characteristic is the abstention rate from the electoral process in Greece (Fig. 1.1).

Fig. 1.1: Election Abstention in Greece.

These indicators of abstinence are interesting. It is clear that awareness is constantly reduced over the years. Even in the 2012 election, amid a very serious Greek crisis, abstinence was higher than ever. This indifference must somehow be interpreted. As Beard and Schultz wrote (1912):

“The smallness of the vote in many instances indicates not a lack of interest but a high degree of intelligence on the part of the voters. It often shows that the voters are aware of the fact that they do not know enough about some particular or local matter to warrant their expressing an opinion one way or another.”

Abstention means moving away from politics because of an indifference, which, in our opinion, is created by a malfunction of democracy. The citizen

decides to abstain from politics since he feels that he has no real effect on the political process. This has to do with the quality of information received. The media is not acting properly and as a result they stop playing the crucial role of the intermediate between citizens and politicians. This probably happens since citizens no longer trust the media, considering that they have lost their objectivity that democracy demands. When information is inadequate, or targeted to a non objectively direction, it creates a gap of trust between media and society.

Democracy requires awareness of conscience and a sense of citizen responsibility. This is theoretical premise and practical necessity. When in a regime that has been created by the citizens and for the citizens themselves, the sense of responsibility to the state no longer exists, democracy loses its real meaning. The sense of responsibility, however, relates to information provided and received by the citizen. Citizens can't be activated for a constitutional need that they don't or they are not allowed to know. As aptly pointed out by Luciano Floridi (2005):

“Consider first the crucial role played by information as a resource for as moral evaluations and actions.”

Citizens are responsible when stay inactive on political issues that are aware of. This cannot be true for issues not known to them and perhaps the significant level of abstention is related. Citizens have a minimum and low level information input for very serious and critical issues of the state, that apparently are considered too “deep” for the “layman”. That means that the state considers citizens to be inadequate for serious political act. But gradual separation of citizens from vital state information, disables them from being politically active and creates a feeling and a conscience of apathy that for the case of authoritarian regimes Ivan Krastev (2011) identifies as “Zombie authoritarianism”. A term employed in cases of authoritarian or undemocratic regimes, because the lack of adequate information and the feeling of apathy it creates to citizens, are attributes of such regimes, clearly not democratic. For instance, the accentuation of the news on the economy because of the timeliness of this topic due to world economic crisis leaves the citizens with no information on many other critical issues of democracy. The over-consumption and the accentuation of the importance of the economy, creates consciences looking exclusively in that direction. As shown in the figure below (Fig. 1.2), Russian citizens consider a very strong state economy to be more important than a strong and well-founded democracy.

This tendency of course, has to do with the information received by Russian citizens, since Russia, as shown below, is strictly controlled by the Putin administration. In a democracy, active and capable citizen is considered one that is able to be properly informed (Floridi, 2005) and hence, act properly.

Fig. 1.2: Riches over Rights.

What is more important?
% of Russians polled responding:

Source: Pew Research Centre

Democracy and information are two concepts directly associated, promoting and reinforcing one another. Therefore, a constitution is not considered democratic when it does not allow, directly or not, for its citizens to receive clear and unbiased information. Any attempt to control information provided to citizens implies totalitarianism.

1.2. Propaganda as the enemy of Democracy.

As discussed above, democracy and information are two concepts closely connected and interdependent from each other. But what happens when one of these two is suppressed? Could they exist independently of each other? In the modern history of the last 100 years, where the Western states progressively became democratic, freedom of the press developed into a serious demand on the part of citizens who experienced, after many centuries of oppression, the constitutional establishment of their rights and freedoms. Pluralism and freedom of expression and information were considered basic principles of democratic states. But this freedom introduced in the democratic societies found no space in totalitarian regimes. Where there is no pluralism and freedom of expression there is the only admissible voltage and ideology. In Nazi Germany of Hitler there was the propaganda ministry headed by Goebbels (Mann, 2004). Through this the Nazis channelled information and news that could support and define the common sense of the opinions and theories of Nazism. So did the Stalin's communist Russia, where the only acceptable ideology within the state, was that of communism. And that is the definition of propaganda.

But we don't need to go back in history to look how totalitarian regimes manage information. In today's Turkey and Russia, two countries that claim to be democratic states, media monitoring and information dissemination in general are obviously directed. But first we need to see why it is so important for authoritarian regimes to impose an ideology and control information.

Certainly the modern totalitarian regimes have learned from history that excessive repression and coercion by methods of violence, leads mathematically to social explosion, with negative results for those in power. So, along with the booming of the media and particularly television, the totalitarian governments are trying to impose indirectly their principles and beliefs. Through the control of information, they can form the conscience they want and as they wish, throughout generations with very little chance of questioning on the part of citizens.

Apart for advertising the authorities of a totalitarian regime, an even more important function of media manipulation is to identify and prevent the public from any potentially damaging perception for the status quo. As it was noted by Christopher Walker and Robert Ortung (2014):

“State-controlled media do not exist solely to praise the powers that be, however. A vital companion function is to trust and discredit alternatives to the authoritarian status quo before these can gain traction with citizens at large. In this way, state-run media are a tool for marginalizing any potential political opposition or civic movement.”

This function of media is extremely important and illustrates how most modern dictators think and act, since they prefer more indirect means of control. However, knowing that they can't impose their ideology on the whole population, they are trying to disarm political dynamics of dissidents, also by an indirect way, i.e. for those they can't persuade and control, they seek to form a consciousness of political apathy. They prefer to create a culture of apolitical citizens to their state, to discourage them from potential overthrow thoughts and democratic inquiries. As Christopher Walker and Robert Ortung (2014) also points out:

“State-dominated media work to make mass audiences respect and fear the regime, but just as important is the task of breeding apathy and passivity.”

Here we can identify the basic difference between democracy and dictatorship. In the case of democracy, political apathy is a very serious disease of government that needs to be addressed, while in dictatorships apathy is what those governments seek for. At this point of course, we should note that there is a huge wave of political apathy in traditional western democracies, which reveals a problem that needs be further addressed.

The figure below (Fig.1.3) shows that abstinence from the democratic process of elections is an increasing phenomenon in almost all the traditional democratic countries of the West. The percentage of non-politicized citizens in democratic Europe and America, could be enviable for the modern totalitarian regimes, where main goal is to keep the greatest possible proportion of citizens away from political consciousness (Hirschman, 1991).

Fig. 1.3: Democratic disillusion.

Tactics used in totalitarian regimes to maintain apathy and disorient citizens are many. In modern Russia's ostensible democracy, Putin's government uses sideways strategies to bypass any information about political activism that contradicts to the center-line of government (Walker & Ortung, 2014). To attain this, the government employs various practices. For example the most important media in complete control by the government, show entertainment programs while an antigovernment demonstration takes place in Moscow's center. To comprehend what this implies, we have to take into account the vastness of the Russian region and the separation that differentiates the largest percentage of the population from scenes where important political developments and reactions take place. As a result, large populations can only be informed through media and Internet use (Mickiewicz, 2008). According to measurements, 88% of the Russian population is informed through television while only 47.7% use the Internet (www.internetworldstats.com 2013). This indicates that a significant proportion of citizens is informed through the central news highlighting channels that are in absolute control of the government (Mickiewicz, 2008). That means that the average Russian citizen receives an image that government media-controlled agencies create and doesn't know the real facts, since the limelight news can't reach him. Considering the fairly small percentage of Internet users, we understand that there are not many chances for real and unbiased information. The paradox in this case is that while about 49% of citizens informed by the TV, declare they are sceptical about the objectivity of the traditional media

(Mickiewicz, 2008), at the same time they show political apathy and insist being informed by these unreliable (as they state) sources. This signifies the effectiveness of central authority practices. Although a large proportion of Russians seems to understand that under the lines of information they receive lays a manipulated political approach, they appear to be convinced that it is impossible to alter this circumstance. As rightly noted by Christopher Walker and Robert Ortung (2014):

“Large majorities have absorbed the idea that they can do little to change the situation. They remain apathetic and apolitical.”

This is exactly the fact mentioned above. For example, when central government is unable to convince of the correctness of its policy, it prefers to poison their political consciousness and make them apathetic towards crucial events. This ensures smooth governance and stability, without worrying that the ruling will have to face future social explosion demanding true democracy. Turkish citizens confront a similar situation. Erdogan's government is in direct interaction with the most important media channels and their objectivity depends on whether media-owners are doing business with the government (Walker & Ortung, 2014). That infers media is controlled completely by central administration. A very good example of this is when in June 2013 during mass protest in Taksim Square, major government controlled television networks were broadcasting animal life documentaries. This, as in the case of Russia, means that in a country like Turkey, the largest proportion of the population informed by TV could have never realized the extent and the intensity of such anti-government protests. At this point we should note that in Turkey, only 45.7% of the active population makes use of the Internet (www.internetworldstats.com, 2013).

These reveal tactics of totalitarian regimes and the kind of relation with impartial and biased information dissemination. In fact, timely and reliable information dissemination is principal opponent of such regimes and a strong ally to democracy. The issue of information is vital as it can guide and control political behaviors, or conceal phenomena of anti-government political activism. Tactics authoritarian regimes used in the past have today been abandoned, as today's authoritarians, no longer seek the control of the media in an extreme and violent way but by an indirect one, that seems to be more efficient and can create an illusion of objectivity and freedom of the press to citizens (Brady, 2010).

This is the tactic of the totalitarian regimes who do not want democracy by definition. They are not interested in whether they can convince their citizens in keeping them in a state of a passive receiver of events they control. But what happens if in a democracy, the sources of information have completely lost their credibility and viewed as government-controlled institutions? In cases of non-democratic regimes, this practice is very likely. But how can we

identify similar instances of media manipulation in countries that are considered democratic?

2.1. Information through the Internet and Democracy.

The ties of media owners to powerful business interests that relate to elected governments made citizens skeptical as they are not convinced for the freedom of the media that is implied in a democracy. A VPRC's (2013) research recorded distrust of Greek citizens towards media.

Figure 2.1: *Greek citizens towards the media*

<i>“There is a general view that claims that large and basic media in our country do not inform objectively the citizens, but mainly serve the interests of their owners. Will you personally say that you agree or disagree with this opinion?”</i>	Percentage %
Agree	79%
Quite agree	12%
Quite disagree	3%
Disagree	3%
Don't have opinion	3%

Source VPRC (January 2013)

According to the table above (Fig. 2.1), 79% of Greek citizens declare their mistrust to information provided by media and believe they don't serve their democratic values for free and unbiased information. In the same survey, the largest percentage of respondents answered they consider Internet neutral and independent source of information.

Figure 2.2: *Internet as a source of Information*

<i>“Personally what medium do you trust more for your information?”</i>	Percentage %
Internet	39%
TV	32%
Newspapers	9%
radio	8%
None	11%

Source VPRC (January 2013)

Although Internet is considered to be the most reliable and independent information medium, the proportion of the Internet users is still small, with a growing trend. Internet is a relatively new medium, slowly gaining public confidence and regarded as the most independent source of information. For this reason, we consider it as a very important ally of democracy and a central future “player”.

Freedom and pluralism of views offered on the web make Internet an essential democratic tool in the present and especially in the future. The role of social media (Facebook, Twitter) is becoming increasingly important, as indicated by protesting "Indignants", especially in southern European countries, as they were motivated and organized mainly through Facebook. Another good example are events that took place in Arab countries, known as the Arab Spring, whose development and organization, was based entirely on social media (Khondker, 2011).

Revealing incredible energy, movements developed and shaped through the Internet and social media, overturned regimes in power for decades (as in Arab Spring) and influenced hundreds of thousands of citizens to protest in central squares of South European states (i.e. the Indignants). Today, large proportion of citizens using the Internet, consider it is the most impartial source of information (Moor, 2005). Another reason that explains why Internet gains preference over other media, is because fora and blogs highlight and discuss issues that otherwise either fall off or intentionally are ignored (Bohman, 2004). According to Michael Schudson (2005), this has to do with the subjectivity of journalists and the close relationship they develop with politicians, since as he notes:

“There is a real danger for democracy here: namely that, journalists and politicians, because they are so closely linked, have their own, narrow, idea of what the media should cover and they ignore the interests of the people.”

At one point this seems to be normal, but conceals a real threat to democracy, creating a gap between common will and power and in a way, manipulates information that citizens receive, in a manner inconsistent with democracy (Walker & Ortung, 2014). Internet fills this gap through pluralism and freedom of expression and information. For this reason, the web is considered by many scholars a tool that can enhance and improve democracy. The truth is, that at this point in time, the effective influence of Internet, is relatively weak (Bohman, 2004). These millions of voices and opinions expressed in Internet sites are lost and not taken into consideration by the politicians. As Christopher Walker and Robert Ortung (2014) write:

“The Internet, by contrast, is a cacophony of many discordant voices-not the best platform for promoting a unified, coherent opposition to the powers that be.”

This is due to lack of a formal/central institutional arrangement where citizens can express their opinions, obligating politicians to follow the common will. Possibly a well organized and promoted web portal (i.e. “E-ekklesia” , see Mpoitsis, et.al., 2014) could aid citizens to participate in politics actively

through “referendums” and exercise their political obligation and right of political control. This could promote the democratic consciousness and to guide democracy to its real essence, that is, direct and active participation of citizens in political processes. At this point it should be noted that the government of PASOK made a fair effort in this direction by creating <http://www.lab.opengov.gr>. A website where citizens could express their opinion and be informed about political issues. Unfortunately this wasn't a very successful effort as there was not adequate citizen participation. We believe that low participation was observed not due to indifference, but because citizens were not convinced their participation would have any special significance in policy decision making. Even critics of direct democracy, who believe that citizens are inadequate to cope with the modern political requirements, ignoring of course that this by definition eliminates the concept of democracy, consider Internet a tool that can assist representative democracy, since the common will can be recorded directly and easily from politicians who represent them.

From the above, becomes obvious that Internet encompasses a major political issue. Its continuously growing momentum and the common belief that it is an independent medium, transforms it to an extremely valuable tool of democracy. Its value has been understood by those who are in political power, since, especially in totalitarian regimes, there is an attempt to control Internet (i.e. closure of Twitter by Erdogan), while on the side of democratic regimes, it is becoming a real useful and efficient medium mainly during election campaigns (recent example is the election campaigns of Obama). Free Internet information “captures” citizens and provides them with a place where they feel unbound from trivial and, according to their opinion, controlled information. But what are the issues arising from the use of Internet as a source of information? And what are the new challenges it creates?

2.2 Group polarization

A first problem identified by scholars, is that of *Group polarization*. It means that just because Internet users can fetch sought after information, usually they receive partial views. It has been observed that Internet users are directed to sources that are familiar with the concepts and political beliefs they have already formed. Such focus on sources of information with specific direction excludes alternative Internet channels and objectivity in general (Bikhchandani et. al., 1998).

This is a major problem, since key principle of democracy is civilized dialogue and exchange of diverse views. Of course, a contrary argument is that Internet provides at least the possibility of expressing a different opinion that, even if it belongs to a minority group, can be directly expressed. This function is not offered by conventional media.

Except for distracting citizens from opposite views, it has been observed that online information sources of concrete view and ideology lead to extreme behaviors (Sunstein, 2007). It is not a coincidence that Internet developed also to a shelter for many extremist views. As Sunstein (2007) notes:

“Group polarization is occurring every day on the Internet. Indeed, it is clear that the Internet is serving, for many, as a breeding ground for extremism, precisely because like-minded people are deliberating with one another, without hearing contrary views.”

This clearly constitutes a issue that must be properly addressed. However, in our opinion, this is a matter of political culture as well. Even extremist ideologies, were shaped as a result of social-political injustice or even more, because of exclusion of some group or ideologies by the media. So it's not Internet that is causing the problem, since it is a medium where groups can express ideas freely. Therefore, the control of Internet is not therapy. The examination of causes leading people to such opinions should be the first step for the “cure”. In many cases, movements labeled extremist ideologies, as in the case of abolition of slavery and the movement for the equal rights of all men, offered helping hand in guaranteeing certain rights, which admittedly today are of high significance (Sunstein, 2007). This, of course, does not mean that all the extremists have good intentions and fight for fair cause.

2.3 Personalization

Information distribution from specific, limited sources, essentially eliminates the possibility of conciliation and transmission of diverse ideas and views and produces what is called *personalization* (Sunstein, 2007). Internet can provide freedom of information and expression, but, according to several scholars, it prevents users from personal contact with fellow citizens, as in the case of ancient Greek “Agora” where democracy was first shaped. Here we observe a paradox. Albeit Internet is an ally of democracy, bringing together millions of people and creating a modern “ecclesia” in the municipality where views and information change dynamically and without intermediaries, it generates “political socialization” turning the person to himself and leading it to lose contact with other's opinions. It is also worth noting the same could happen if a person reads and gets informed by a particular newspaper or a TV channel. We believe Internet does not cause this issue but simply highlights it.

2.4 Filtering

The last issue that we examine is *filtering*. It is related to huge amounts of information Internet provides for skimming by citizen-users. Generally it is believed that all uploaded Internet material to be valid (Floridi & Sunders, 2004). This has to do with the generalization that Internet is a highly unbound and independent information medium. This of course does not mean that any information provided via Internet is true. But how can the public understand and filter the real information? According to Posner (2005) this is not a major problem, as most of Internet users know that bloggers are in their majority amateur “journalists” and that information they post is not guaranteed to be

valid. This is true but somehow outworn, since it is known to Internet users, but not always easy to distinguish valid from invalid information (Goldman, 2005).

This raises the following question: is it necessary and acceptable for the state to interfere on the issue of filtering, or it is considered censorship and restriction of the role of Internet as an independent medium? Any intervention on the part of the state would make Internet, similar to other media, which pass through filtering, but seem to have lost credibility. We believe that state's central aim should be the creation of emocratic political consciousness that prepares citizens to constructively collect and filter information and opinions received.

Alvin Goldman (2007) notes that today most people are not looking for true information, but simply information that confirms their existing perception. We agree with this and we believe that the state can shape, via education, a truly democratic culture which is based on forming opinions and perceptions through dialogue and proposals rather than an advanced ideological trend that has nothing substantial to offer.

Conclusions

Key issue in a democracy is Information and the media is responsible for properly reporting it to citizens. In a democracy, citizens should be informed promptly and accurately so to properly assess political circumstances and needs of their state. The role of informing citizens has been taken by the media. But during the past, confidence on the part of society has been lost, since it is believed that most of conventional media are mouthpieces of government interests and of entrepreneurs who interact with it. But as the reliability of conventional media decreases, that of Internet as a source of information, is growing. This indicates a trend that must be taken into account with proper care.

Internet is becoming major source of information and the most important channel for opinion exchange. With proper use, it can contribute to the improvement of democracy and why not, it could lead to a more direct structure, where citizens will have an active role in shaping state's policy. But if it is to maintain people's trust and preference it should be insured that Internet will retain its independent characteristics. We think that constitutes weakness on behalf of democratic governments to try to control, even with the excuse of filtering, information and opinions expressed via the web. That is because freedom of expression is exactly the reason why the Internet "captures" peoples trust. Of course it is crucial for democratic states, to create an educational system that promotes a culture of civilized discussion and opinion exchange so future citizens will have the ability to filter information acquired through Internet.

Finally, issues concerning group polarization and personalization are not created by Internet, but originate from social problems related to a range socio-political circumstances.

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